

Thermodynamic Equilibrium Constants of Ternary Chelates of Trivalent La-, Ce-, Pr-, Nd- and Y-EGTA-Amino Acid Systems

VISHNU KOLHE and K DWIVEDI*

School of Studies in Chemistry, Jiwaji University, Gwalior-474 011

Manuscript received 8 November 1994, revised 3 April 1995, accepted 22 May 1995

The trivalent lanthanides are attractive for these studies due to their high charge and their large and variable coordination number. The ligands, ethylene glycol bis(2-aminoethyl ether)tetra acetic acid (EGTA), leucine, norleucine and isoleucine have been chosen because of their biological importance and complex forming ability with several metal ions¹.

Results and Discussion

Representative set of experimental titration curves obtained according to the sequence described in the experimental section for the La^{III}-H₂EGTA²⁻ (disodium salt of ethylene glycol bis(2-aminoethyl ether)tetraacetic acid) - leucine system studied is shown in Fig. 1 Curve-c represents the titration curve of 1 : 1 La^{III}-H₂EGTA²⁻ system. It is observed that curve-c diverges from the H₂EGTA²⁻ ligand titration curve-b in the initial stages of titration followed by a well-defined inflection at $a = 2$, ($a =$ moles of alkali used per mole of ligand/metal) and $\text{pH} \approx 5.0$, indicating the formation of La^{III}-EGTA⁻ complex.

This complex remains stable upto high pH value (9.8) and does not undergo hydrolysis upto this stage.

Examination of titration curve-e (Fig. 1) reveals the formation of the La^{III}-leucine binary complex in the pH range 6.5-7.5 and at $0 \leq a \leq 1$. This is indicated by divergence of the 1 : 1 binary La^{III}-leucine titration curve-e from that of the corresponding ligand (leucine) titration curve-d. Generally such complexes are stable upto $\text{pH} \approx 8.0$. Further, beyond this pH value, hydrolysis of the complexes leads to the formation of monohydroxo and dihydroxo complex species, as evidenced by occurrence of precipitation at $a = 3$ and $\text{pH} \approx 9.5$. Equilibria for these complexation and hydrolysis reactions may be represented as

Algebraic method² has been used to obtain the values of proton dissociation constant of various ligands and formation constant of binary complexes, while Bjerrum's functions³ were used to calculate hydrolysis constant of the complexes (Table 1).

Careful examination of the titration curve-f (Fig. 1) of the mixed ligand complexes reveals that the mixed ligand titration curve runs superimposed on the theoretical composite curve-T from $\text{pH} 2.6$ to 8.0 , indicating that no ternary complex is formed and 1 : 1 M(III)-EGTA complex is formed in the first buffer region, i.e. $0 \leq a \leq 2$, $\text{pH} \approx 3.0-5.0$, which is stable upto high pH value ≈ 8.0 . Above $\text{pH} \approx 8.0$, the mixed ligand titration curve, however, is displaced towards the right of the composite curve-T, suggesting the

Fig. 1 Potentiometric titration curves of La-EGTA-L' system

NOTE

TABLE 1

Proton dissociation constant	$\mu = 0.15$		$\mu = 0.10$		$\mu = 0.05$		$\mu \rightarrow 0$	
	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₁	pK ₂
A	8.73	10.53	8.86	10.5	9.05	10.62	9.18	10.75
L ¹	9.55		9.79		10.04		10.28	
L ²	9.58		9.82		10.07		10.31	
L ³	9.65		9.86		10.11		10.34	
Binary complexes :		$\log K_{MA}^M$		$\log K_{MA}^M$		$\log K_{MA}^M$		$\log K_{MA}^M$
La ^{III} -A		15.25		15.37		15.47		15.552
Ce ^{III} -A		15.64		15.75		15.83		15.92
Pr ^{III} -A		15.75		15.85		15.93		16.02
Nd ^{III} -A		15.91		16.08		16.14		16.24
Sm ^{III} -A		16.46		16.54		16.65		16.74
Y ^{III} -A		16.85		16.95		17.04		17.10
		$\log K_{ML}^M$		$\log K_{ML}^M$		$\log K_{ML}^M$		$\log K_{ML}^M$
La ^{III} -L ¹		5.01		5.13		5.24		5.33
Ce ^{III} -L ¹		5.24		5.38		5.48		5.55
Pr ^{III} -L ¹		5.38		5.48		5.50		5.70
Nd ^{III} -L ¹		5.53		5.61		5.74		5.844
Sm ^{III} -L ¹		5.72		5.82		5.93		6.04
Y ^{III} -L ¹		5.92		6.00		6.13		6.23
La ^{III} -L ²		5.13		5.25		5.35		5.50
Ce ^{III} -L ²		5.35		5.42		5.57		5.60
Pr ^{III} -L ²		5.42		5.52		5.62		5.72
Nd ^{III} -L ²		5.60		5.70		5.81		5.90
Sm ^{III} -L ²		5.76		5.89		5.98		6.12
Y ^{III} -L ²		5.99		6.09		6.19		6.29
La ^{III} -L ³		5.163		5.27		5.37		5.48
Ce ^{III} -L ³		5.374		5.45		5.58		5.67
Pr ^{III} -L ³		5.480		5.55		5.64		5.73
Nd ^{III} -L ³		5.652		5.72		5.83		5.92
Sm ^{III} -L ³		5.823		5.92		5.99		6.09
Y ^{III} -L ³		6.041		6.11		6.21		6.29

A = H₂EGTA²⁻, L = L¹ (norleucine), L² (leucine) or L³ (isoleucine).

liberation of extra protons due to the formation of mixed ligand complex. This behaviour indicates that the binary complex [M(III)-EGTA]⁻ is formed first and it coordinates with leucine/isoleucine/norleucine as secondary ligand to yield the mixed ligand complex [M(III)-EGTA-L]²⁻ in step-wise manner,

where HL = leucine, isoleucine and norleucine. The formation of the ternary complex is further supported by the non-appearance of any solid phase throughout the mixed ligand

TABLE 2—THERMODYNAMIC VALUES OF FIRST AND SECOND HYDROLYSIS CONSTANTS OF METAL-LIGAND COMPLEXES

$\mu \rightarrow 0$, temp. = 25°

Hydrolysis constant	La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}	Y ^{III}
$\log K_{ML_1(OH)}^M$	8.56	8.52	8.49	8.44	8.38	8.35
$\log K_{ML_2(OH)}^M$	8.53	8.48	8.44	8.41	8.36	8.31
$\log K_{ML_3(OH)}^M$	8.50	8.46	8.42	8.39	8.34	8.29
$\log K_{ML_1(OH)_2}^M$	9.04	9.96	8.91	8.87	8.84	8.79
$\log K_{ML_2(OH)_2}^M$	9.01	8.94	8.88	8.85	8.81	8.76
$\log K_{ML_3(OH)_2}^M$	8.98	8.93	8.86	8.82	8.78	8.74

L¹ = norleucine, L² = leucine, L³ = isoleucine.

TABLE 3

Mixed-ligand Complex	log K_{MAL}^{MA}				$\Delta \log K$	% RS
	$\mu = 0.15M$	$\mu = 0.05M$	$\mu = 0.05M$	$\mu \rightarrow 0$		
La ^{III} -AL ¹	3.37	3.50	3.59	3.69	-1.64	-30.77
Ce ^{III} -AL ¹	3.44	3.57	3.64	3.76	-1.79	32.25
Pr ^{III} -AL ¹	3.59	3.69	3.74	3.83	-1.87	-32.81
Nd ^{III} -AL ¹	3.75	3.88	3.57	4.06	-1.78	-30.48
Sm ^{III} -AL ¹	3.92	4.08	4.13	4.22	-1.82	-30.13
Y ^{III} -AL ¹	4.04	4.16	4.28	4.39	-1.84	-29.53
La ^{III} -AL ²	3.44	3.52	2.89	3.70	-1.86	-32.73
Ce ^{III} -AL ²	3.48	3.60	3.68	3.77	-1.83	-32.68
Pr ^{III} -AL ²	3.60	3.71	3.78	3.84	-1.88	-32.87
Nd ^{III} -AL ²	3.77	3.90	3.999	4.00	-1.90	-32.20
Sm ^{III} -AL ²	3.98	4.10	4.17	4.27	-1.85	-30.23
Y ^{III} -AL ²	4.07	4.20	4.29	4.42	-1.78	-28.71
La ^{III} -AL ³	3.55	3.56	3.63	3.71	-1.75	-32.05
Ce ^{III} -AL ³	3.54	3.65	3.72	3.78	-1.85	-33.33
Pr ^{III} -AL ³	3.70	3.73	3.75	3.83	-1.90	-33.16
Nd ^{III} -AL ³	3.79	3.92	4.01	4.04	-1.88	-31.77
Sm ^{III} -AL ³	3.99	4.13	4.19	4.27	-1.82	-29.89
Y ^{III} -AL ³	4.10	4.22	4.30	4.40	-1.89	-30.05

A = H₂EGTA²⁻; L = L¹ (norleucine), L² (leucine) or L³ (isoleucine).

titration system. The values of proton-dissociation constant and metal-ligand stability constant were used for the calculation of equilibrium constant of the ternary complexes. The species present in solution were considered to be H₂A²⁻, HA³⁻, HL, L⁻, MA⁻, ML²⁺ and MAL²⁻. The formation of ternary complexes can also be evidenced by representative species distribution curves for the La(III)-EGTA-leucine system and it is observed that in the pH range 3.0–8.0, M³⁺ and MA⁻ are the major species while in the pH range 8.0–10.0, the major species are MA⁻ and MAL²⁻. The value of proton-dissociation constant of ligands, stability constant of binary and ternary complexes are presented in Tables 1–3 along with $\Delta \log K = (\log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M)$ and percentage of relative stabilisation,

$$(\%) \text{ R.S.} = (\Delta \log K / \log K_{ML}^M) \times 100$$

The negative values of (%) R.S. indicate that the secondary ligand binds better to aquometal ion [M(III)(H₂O)_n]³⁺ than the binary [M-EGTA]⁻ complex. Such lowering of stability of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complex as compared to that of 1 : 1 binary complex is probable due to large size of the primary ligand, destabilisation effect caused by the repulsion between 1 : 1 binary [M(III)-EGTA]⁻ and incoming negatively charged secondary ligand (L⁻) coupled with the lesser number of coordinating sites for the second ligand on [M(III), EGTA]⁻ as compared to free [M(III)(H₂O)_n]³⁺ metal ions.

The value of the dissociation constants of the ligands (pK_a) decreases with increases in ionic strength of the medium, which is in accordance with Debye-Hückel equation⁵.

$$(pK_a^0 - [A \mu^{1/2} / (1 + \mu^{1/2})] + e\mu) = pK_a$$

Similar trends of variation have been observed in the case of stability constants of binary and ternary complexes.

Stability order of binary and ternary complexes is found to be in accordance with increasing ionic potential of metal(III) ions, i.e. La < Ce < Pr < Nd < Sm < Y, and the stability sequence with respect to secondary ligand follows the basicity order of the ligands, i.e. isoleucine > leucine > norleucine.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade and the solution were prepared in double-distilled CO₂-free water. Stock solutions of the ligands Na₂H₂EGTA, norleucine, leucine and isoleucine were prepared. The metal(III) nitrate solutions were prepared and standardised⁶. The pH-titrations were made with an Elico LI-120 pH meter (accuracy + 0.01 pH unit) having glass and calomel electrodes assembly. The pH meter was calibrated with standard buffer solutions of pH 4.00 and 9.20. The following titration mixtures were used : (i), HNO₃ (2.0 × 10⁻³ M); (ii), (i) + ligand H₂EGTA²⁻ (1.0 × 10⁻³ M); (iii), (ii) + metal(III) ion (1.0 × 10⁻³ M); (iv), (i) + ligand HL (1.0 × 10⁻³ M); (v), (iv) + metal(III) ion (1.0 × 10⁻³ M); (vi), HNO₃ (2.0 × 10⁻³ M) + ligand H₂EGTA²⁻ (1.0 × 10⁻³ M) + ligand HL (1.0 × 10⁻³ M) + metal(III) ion (1.0 × 10⁻³ M). The initial volume of each titration mixture was kept 50.0 ml. The required amount of NaNO₃ solution was added to each titration mixture to get the desired ionic strengths, i.e. 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15 M. All the solutions were thermostated at 25 ± 0.2° and titrated against standard NaOH solution (0.10 M).

NOTE

References

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